

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

The Nobel prize and its consequences

Carlos Navarro Venegas *

Faculty of Veterinary Sciences (FAVET). University of Chile, Chile.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2022, 15(01), 568–570

Publication history: Received on 22 June 2022; revised on 24 July 2022; accepted on 26 July 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2022.15.1.0757>

Abstract

The origin of the Nobel Prize dates back to 1895, when Alfred Nobel made his last will and testament, donating most of his fortune to a series of prizes in Physics, Chemistry, Physiology or Medicine, Literature and Peace. However, the first was delivered in 1901 and since then every December 10, the date Nobel died.

It is then a very precious achievement for some scientists and scholars who are nominated each year for their contributions in different disciplines and who, by being recognized by the Swedish Academy, go on to immortality, both in research and in university teaching at least.

Keywords: Nobel Prize; Immortality; Worldwide recognition; University status

1. Introduction

But who was this current Patron of Science? Alfred Nobel (1833-1896) was a Swedish chemist, engineer and businessman, who in 1867 created dynamite, a plastic explosive resulting from absorbing nitroglycerin in a porous solid material, thereby reducing the risk of an accident (in one of which his own brother Emil had died). Nobel patented all his inventions and founded companies to manufacture and market them since 1865. Thus, Nobel accumulated enormous wealth, but also a certain guilt complex for the evil and destruction that his inventions could have caused humanity on the battlefields. The combination of both reasons led him to bequeath his fortune to a foundation -the Nobel Foundation, created in 1900- with the task of awarding a series of annual prizes to the people who had done the most for the benefit of humanity in the fields of physics, chemistry, medicine, literature, and peace [1].

2. Results

This award is the most important that some of the scientists and other good people have received. Those who have received it twice stand out and until now, only four people could boast of it: Frederick Sanger, Linus Pauling, John Bardeen and Marie Curie.

In the field of Medicine or Physiology, mention should be made of Robert Koch (1905), Camilo Golgi (1906), Alexander Fleming (1945), Hans Krebs (1953), Joshua Lederberg (1958), James Watson and Francis Crick (1962), André Lwoff (1965), Salvatore Luria (1969), David Baltimore, Renato Dulbecco and Edward Temin (1972), César Milstein (1984), Stanley Prusiner (1997), Luc Montagnier (2008) [1].

In the field of Chemistry it is necessary to remember Ernest Rutherford (1908), Marie Curie (1911), Wendell Stanley (1946), Linus Pauling (1954), Frederick Sanger (1958), Melvin Calvin (1961), Frederick Sanger (1980) and Kary Mullis (1993) [1].

* Corresponding author: Carlos Navarro Venegas; Email: canavarr@uchile.cl
Faculty of Veterinary Sciences (FAVET). University of Chile, Chile.

Several of these winners are known through our undergraduate courses, such as, for example, some related to: tuberculosis, cellular organelles, penicillin, the Krebs cycle, DNA theory, *viruses are viruses*, prions and HIV on the one hand; and others for the atomic model, radioactivity, the crystallization of viruses, the sequencing of the first genome and for an invention that revolutionized Molecular Biology: the Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) [2].

Currently, the Universities are numbered according to the Shanghai Ranking and one of the parameters it considers is how many Nobel laureates there are in its ranks [3].

3. Discussion

Located in the USA and founded as a district of Los Angeles in 1910, Hollywood is the mecca of cinema worldwide, being the most important film industry in the world. The first studio in the Hollywood area was founded in 1911 and during that same year another fifteen studios were established there [4].

The cinema has not been oblivious to the biomedical and mathematical advances of Humanity.

Thus, it is possible to mention some Hollywood productions such as *Madame Curie* (1943), *A Beautiful Mind* (2001) in reference to John Nash, Nobel Prize in Economics Sciences (1994); or Alan Turing, a brilliant English mathematician in *The Imitation Game* (2014).

I have left for last Joshua Lederberg, molecular biologist (1925-2008) who pointed out that the greatest concrete threat to man's permanent domination of the planet is a virus.

His phrase appears on the screen at the beginning of the movie *Outbreak* (1995), in which a pandemic puts Humanity on the ropes. Does it sound like you? (Covid19).

Of all the winners, Kary Mullis stands out, whose brilliant invention has been part of several final works of Veterinary Medicine students and there are those who mention that the above allows to separate the study of diseases as before and after the PCR [5, 6, 7, 8, 9]

4. Conclusion

The Nobel Prize grants perpetuity to a surname or rather to human intelligence. It is to be expected that advances in biomedicine will increase.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

We thank the FAVET students (for achieving part of their dreams with us) and the Wolf Foundation, Illinois, USA (since 2020).

References

- [1] The Nobel Prize. [Internet]. Nobelprize.org; © 2022 [cited 2022 July 12]. Available from: <https://www.nobelprize.org/>
- [2] Mullis K, Faloona F. Specific synthesis of DNA in vitro via a polymerase catalyzed chain reaction. *Methods in Enzymology* 1987; 155: 335-350.
- [3] Shanghai Ranking Consultancy. [Internet]. Academic Ranking of World Universities. © 2021 [cited 2022 July 11] Available from: <https://www.shanghairanking.com/rankings/arwu/2021>
- [4] EcuRed [Internet]. Ecured © 2022. [cited 2022 July 12]. Available from: <https://www.ecured.cu/Hollywood> (California), 2022.
- [5] Vargas M, Jara MA, Navarro C. Use of primer design to detect the Glycoprotein C gene of Canine Herpes Virus by Polymerase Chain Reaction. *Acta Scientific Veterinary Sciences* 2022, 4 (3): 94-101.

- [6] Salas, V., Pizarro, J., Navarro, C. Phylogenetic analysis of canine distemper virus detected in Chile. 2018 International Journal of Current Research, 2018, 1(08): 72402-72407
- [7] Cisternas F, Navarro C, Jara MA. Feline calicivirus. Molecular detection with primers design. EC Veterinary Science 2020, 5(7): 54-72.
- [8] Carreño C, Navarro C, Jara MA. Design of primers in the molecular detection of Feline Panleukopenia Virus. World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences, 2021, 8(3): 019–029.
- [9] Fuentes A, Jara MA, Navarro C. Detection of ul37 gene from Canine Herpes Virus by Polymerase Chain Reaction. International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Growth Evaluation. 2022, 3(1):401-407